

NMR and Magnetic Susceptibility Studies of Nitro-Ammine Cobalt(III) Complexes

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A series of nitro-ammine cobalt(III) complexes have been reported. The ^{59}Co nuclear magnetic resonance (n.m.r.), magnetic susceptibility and electronic spectra of these complexes were studied. The order of ligand field theory obtained from n.m.r. and residual paramagnetic susceptibility data are in fair agreement with optical data. The ^{59}Co nuclei in the said series of complexes are more shielded than the aquo, carbonato and oxalato series of cobalt(III)-ammine complexes. The deviation of the ^{59}Co chemical shifts and residual paramagnetism versus reciprocal of the energy of the first d-d electron transition is attributed to covalent bonding of ligands configurational interaction (*cis* and *trans*) and low symmetry crystal fields of the complexes.

It has been well known that the trivalent cobalt forms a number of spin paired diamagnetic octahedral complexes. The ^{59}Co n.m.r. chemical shifts and magnetic susceptibility for Co(III) complexes have been reported by earlier workers¹⁻⁸. Recently the residual paramagnetism of cobalt in the few series of Co(III)-ammine complexes was reported elsewhere⁹⁻¹⁰. Since nitro-ammine Co(III) complex series has not been studied so far, a systematic study, in conjunction with n.m.r. magnetic susceptibility and electronic spectra has been reported in this paper.

Materials and Methods :

Preparation of complexes : All the complexes of nitroammine Co(III) were prepared according to the modified methods described elsewhere¹¹ and then purified. The analytical data (Table 1) for the complexes were used for the identification and as a criterion for purity.

Physical measurements : The n.m.r. measurements were made on Varian wide line spectrometer V4200 at about 10,000 gauss. In this set up the homogeneity of the magnetic field over the sample volume and R.F. stability are good enough to give a resolution of better than 50 milligauss and therefore the shifts of the order of a gauss or more can be easily studied. The shift measurements were made in aqueous solution at room temperature ($22 \pm 2^\circ$). The values of chemical shifts ($\sigma\%$) observed for these complexes have been expressed :

$$[H_i - H_r/H_r] \times 100$$

where H_i is the resonance field for cobalt complex under study and H_r for the field of reference compound $\text{K}_3[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6]$ at constant frequency. The electronic spectra of the complexes were taken

on a Hilger Uvispeck spectrophotometer, model H 700, using 1 cm matched quartz cells. The magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes were determined at room temperature by Gouy method, employing pure dried KCl and $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ as calibrants.

Results and Discussion

The observed chemical shifts (σ) for the nitro-ammine Co(III) complexes are given in Table 1. The values are negative since the resonance occurs at a field lower than that for the reference $\text{K}_3[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6]$, and the shifts are quite large about 7,000 to 10,000 ppm relative to reference complex.

The residual paramagnetic contribution (σ_{para}) which is the most dominant term in shielding in Co(III) complexes has been calculated for the complexes under investigation, [column (5), Table I] using the relation given by Griffith and Orgel¹². The data in column (4) can be compared with those in column (5) in which the observed values of relative chemical shifts have been converted to the absolute values by adding σ_{para} for $\text{K}_3[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6]$ (-1.53)⁵.

The results of magnetic susceptibility measurements are given in Table 1. The calculation and other details of these values are given elsewhere⁹. The diamagnetic correction $\Sigma\chi_D$ for the constituent atoms were calculated assuming Pascal's additivity rule for the complexes under study⁹. The choice of these diamagnetic correction values is arbitrary due to divergent reported data in the literature¹⁴ and it is difficult to choose any one value as more reliable than the other.

The results indicate that the observed χ_M values for all the complexes are much smaller than $\Sigma\chi_D$ values. The difference between the two is obviously due to residual paramagnetism due to cobalt. In the n.m.r. method chemical shift depends on the

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TABLE I—ANALYSIS, CHEMICAL SHIFT, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA FOR NITRO-AMMINE Co(III) COMPLEXES

Complex	Found (%)	Cal. (%)	Observed		Calculated	$10X_M$	$\sum \langle D \rangle$	χ_P (obs)	χ_P (cal)	Orbital reduction factor k	Energy separation in cm^{-1} between ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$
			σ values	$\sigma\%$ values							
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{Cl}_2$	Co 22.32 NH ₃ 38.37	22.30 38.20	-0.810	-2.0340	-2.342	63.21	181.6	118.4	194.0	0.76	21050
2. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NO}_2]\text{Cl}_2$	Co 23.41 NH ₃ 32.68	22.60 32.70	-0.752	-2.282	-2.239	40.58	154.6	114.0	185.5	0.78	22030
3. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{ONO}]\text{Cl}_2$	Co 22.29 NH ₃ 32.83	22.58 32.63	-0.870	-2.400	-2.375	32.31	154.6	122.3	196.8	0.79	20750
4. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2]\text{Cl}$ <i>cis</i>	Co 22.92 NH ₃ 26.30	23.12 26.73	-0.715	-2.245	-2.204	86.83	127.6	100.8	182.6	0.74	22370
5. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2]\text{Cl}$ <i>trans</i>	Co 22.96 NH ₃ 26.42	23.12 26.73	-0.688	-2.238	-2.169	31.35	127.7	96.3	179.7	0.73	22720
6. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{ONO})_2]\text{Cl}$ <i>cis</i>	Co 23.33 NH ₃ 26.25	23.12 26.73	-0.898	-2.428	-2.502	20.84	147.6	126.8	207.3	0.78	19760
7. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{H}_2\text{OONO}](\text{NO}_2)_2$ <i>cis</i>	Co 18.54 NH ₃ 21.82	18.75 21.62	-0.971	-2.501	-2.514	14.38	144.8	130.4	203.3	0.79	19610
8. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{H}_2\text{ONO}_2](\text{NO}_2)_2$ <i>cis</i>	Co 18.21 NH ₃ 21.43	18.75 21.62	-0.830	-2.360	-2.336	30.50	144.8	114.3	193.6	0.77	21100
9. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{NO}_2\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$ <i>trans</i>	Co 24.48 NH ₃ 27.71	24.14 27.97	-0.818	-2.348	-2.357	18.78	137.5	118.8	195.4	0.78	20920
10. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_3(\text{NO}_2)_3]$	Co 23.90 NH ₃ 20.63	23.80 20.73	-0.647	-2.177	-2.144	4.89	100.6	95.5	177.7	0.73	22990
11. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{Cl}]$	Co 24.87 NH ₃ 21.03	24.82 21.52	-0.719	-2.249	-2.219	3.513	110.5	107.0	183.9	0.76	22220
12. $\text{Na}[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{NO}_2)_4]$	Co 19.79 NH ₃ 11.11	19.64 11.32	-0.622	-2.152	-2.070	41.51	103.7	92.2	171.6	0.73	23810
13. $\text{Na}_2[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{NO}_2)_5]$	Co 16.58 NH ₃ 4.66	16.74 4.82	-0.610	-2.140	-2.036	18.60	106.6	88.0	168.8	0.71	24210
14. $\text{Na}_3[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$	Co 14.25 N 20.68	14.59 20.80	-0.735	-2.285	-2.385	2.21	107.6	111.8	197.7	0.74	20360

Magnetic Susceptibility data are in the units of -1×10^{-6} cgs.

fact that in the octahedral complexes of Co(III), only one state, namely ${}^1T_{1g}$ of d^6 configuration of cobalt, can mix with the ground state ${}^1A_{1g}$ so that contribution of second order paramagnetism to the shielding parameters depends inversely on the energy separation between the two states. From this study one is inclined to believe that the main contribution to the shifts is the residual paramagnetism while the diamagnetic contribution has minor role in affecting the σ values.

It is seen that the replacement of ammonia ligand by nitro ion in these complexes results on decrease in σ values instead of increase in σ values as in case of aquo³, carbonate⁴ and oxalato⁶ series of Co(III)-amine complexes. Further σ decreases with an increase in the number of nitro groups in the complex $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{Cl}_2$ which means that the shielding increases with substitution of the electro-negative nitro group in the coordination sphere of Co(III) complex. The increase is in the order for nitro-amine Co(III) complexes: hexamine < pentamine < tetramine (*cis* and *trans*) < triamine < mono ammine < hexanitro (without ammonia ligand).

From the Table 1, it is seen that few mixed ligand and few nitritoamine Co(III) complexes

behave differently from the rest of the complexes in this series because of oxygen and chlorine bonding towards cobalt along with nitrogen bonding in the complex moiety.

To compare the above order with the spectral data the absorption spectra of these complexes were studied in the visible region and a weak absorption due to d-d transition was found. The energy separation between the ground state ${}^1A_{1g}$ and excited state ${}^1T_{1g}$ of d^6 configuration was estimated from these bands (Table 1). The values show that the successive replacement of NH_3 ligand by nitro group increase the energy separation between the two states, further E values increases as successively as the number of nitro group in coordination sphere of complex increases. On the same line in magnetic susceptibility data residual paramagnetism value (χ_p) decreases regularly from hexamine to mono ammine (Table 1). Hexanitro cobaltate behaves differently from the rest of the complexes as far as n.m.r., magnetic and electronic spectral data are concerned. This may be due to mixture of nitro and nitrito ligands in the said complex.

The n.m.r., magnetic and electronic data can also be utilized to establish the relative ligand field strength of the ligands such as ONO^- , H_2O , NH_3

and NO_2^- in these complexes (Table 1). From these values, it is inferred that H_2O and ONO^- are weaker than NH_3 and NH_3 is still weaker compared to NO_2^- ligand. The strength of these ligands increases in the order: $\text{H}_2\text{O} > \text{ONO}^- > \text{NH}_3 > \text{NO}_2^-$ in conformity with spectro-chemical series.

From the Table 1, it is also observed that linkage isomers can be more easily distinguished (nitro and nitrito) by n.m.r. method than any other physical methods. The yellow and red varieties of these isomers are known in the literature for nitrite Co(III) complexes. There is chemical shift of 12-18 gauss (at 10 K. gauss) between these isomers. The nitrite-ammine complexes (including mixed ligand nitrite also) of Co(III) exhibit two signals. The intensity of one is more than the other. The weaker signal was due to nitrito complexes and it slowly disappears when the specimen gets old. Similarly this study can be used to distinguish configurational mixing (*cis* and *trans*) (Table 1).

The values of k (orbital reduction factor) are in the range of 0.70-0.80. For pure d orbitals $k=1$ and for low spin complexes of transition series k will close to unity, $(1-k)$ being the measure of the deviation of actual orbitals from being pure orbitals. These values clearly indicate that there is significant orbital overlap. It is also possible to calculate χ_p values from the relation of Griffith¹³. It is seen from the results that the calculated χ_p values are larger than the observed. Griffith and Orgel¹² estimated the probable error (20 per cent) in their theoretical calculations. In some of our complexes the disagreement between χ_p (obs) and χ_p (cal) and

Fig. 1. The variation of chemical shift vs λ_{\max}

even in n.m.r. results is outside the probable error. The theory¹² also predicts a linear relation between the ^{59}Co n.m.r. chemical shift versus the reciprocal of the energy of the first d-d electronic transition (λ_{\max}) and residual paramagnetism (χ_p) versus λ_{\max} (Figs. 1 and 2). It is seen from the figures that the correlation in case of n.m.r. results is fairly good but in magnetic susceptibility, it is not smooth.

Fig. 2. The variation of χ_p (obs) vs λ_{\max}

Eventhough such a linear relationship has been found to be approximately true^{1,2} but the deviations from such a linear relationship now is also known^{15,16}. We believe that main sources of deviations are covalent bonding of ligands in these complexes, uncertainties in the values of diamagnetic susceptibilities used for evaluating term, configurational interaction (*cis* and *trans*) and lastly the distortion in the octahedral ligand field from hexa ammine (O_h) to pentammine (C_{4v}), *trans* tetrammine (D_{4h}), *cis* (C_{2v}), triammine (C_{3v}) etc.

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